

Electrocardiographic Findings, USG Neck and Echocardiography in Hypothyroidism

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Abstract:

Background: Hypothyroidism, a common endocrine disorder characterized by insufficient thyroid hormone production, has wide-ranging effects on various organ systems, particularly the cardiovascular system. The condition is associated with increased risks of cardiovascular diseases, including atherosclerosis, diastolic hypertension, and arrhythmias, which contribute significantly to morbidity and mortality. Despite the known risks, the interplay between thyroid dysfunction and cardiovascular health requires further exploration through comprehensive diagnostic assessments.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate electrocardiographic ECG, neck ultrasound USG, and echocardiographic findings in patients with hypothyroidism to better understand the cardiovascular implications and to inform clinical management strategies.

Methods: Participants underwent standard 12-lead ECG, neck USG, and echocardiography. Data on demographic and clinical characteristics were collected, and statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings, and correlations between diagnostic modalities were analyzed.

Results: The study found that 34% of participants exhibited sinus bradycardia on ECG, with 26% showing prolonged QT intervals and 21.7% displaying low voltage QRS complexes. Neck USG revealed diffuse thyroid enlargement in 60% of participants and hypoechoic texture in 70%. Echocardiography identified left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in 30% of the cohort, with 20% having mild pericardial effusion. Significant correlations were observed between ECG abnormalities and echocardiographic findings, suggesting a close relationship between thyroid dysfunction and cardiac impairment.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates a high prevalence of cardiovascular abnormalities in patients with hypothyroidism, underscoring the importance of routine cardiovascular evaluations in this population. The significant correlations between ECG, USG, and echocardiographic findings highlight the need for integrated diagnostic approaches to improve early detection and management of cardiovascular risks in hypothyroid patients.

Recommendations: Clinicians should adopt a multidisciplinary approach to managing hypothyroidism, incorporating regular cardiovascular assessments using ECG, neck USG, and echocardiography. Further research is recommended to explore the long-term outcomes of early cardiovascular interventions in hypothyroid patients.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, Cardiovascular Disease, Electrocardiography, Echocardiography, Thyroid Ultrasound

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Introduction

Millions of people worldwide suffer from hypothyroidism, a common endocrine ailment marked by insufficient production of thyroid hormone. Thyroid hormone is essential for controlling metabolism, and a lack of it can cause a variety of physiological problems. Hypothyroidism can present with mild symptoms like weight gain and exhaustion or with more serious ones like

myxedema and cardiovascular problems. Hypothyroidism is linked to a number of comorbidities because of the systemic character of the illness, especially cardiovascular conditions, which are a major source of morbidity and mortality in this population.

The intricate connection between hypothyroidism and cardiovascular health has been brought to light by recent research. It is well recognised that hypothyroidism raises the risk of cardiovascular events by causing changes in lipid metabolism, diastolic hypertension, and atherosclerosis.

Moreover, variations in thyroid hormone levels can have a significant impact on the cardiovascular system. Heart failure, coronary artery disease, and arrhythmias have been linked to even subclinical hypothyroidism, where hormone levels are only slightly lowered. Patients with hypothyroidism often experience changes in their ECG, such as sinus bradycardia, low voltage QRS complexes, and prolonged QT intervals. These ECG abnormalities may be early signs of underlying heart dysfunction. Another useful technique for studying hypothyroidism is USG, which is especially useful for assessing thyroid morphology. Common findings in hypothyroid individuals include thyroid enlargement, nodularity, and changes in echotexture, which can shed light on the aetiology of the illness, which may include Hashimoto's disease or autoimmune thyroiditis.

Furthermore, it is impossible to overestimate the importance of echocardiography in determining how hypothyroidism affects the heart. Hypothyroid individuals frequently report echocardiographic abnormalities such as left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, pericardial effusion, and left ventricular hypertrophy, which emphasises the importance of a thorough cardiac evaluation in this population. The relationship between thyroid function and cardiovascular health has been the subject of more research in recent years, with an increased emphasis on early detection and intervention. For example, prompt thyroid hormone replacement therapy may reduce some of the cardiovascular risks associated with hypothyroidism, particularly in older persons. [1].

In a similar vein, Chaker meta-analysis shown that treating subclinical hypothyroidism may lower the incidence of heart failure in specific high-risk groups [2]. This study aims to ECG, USG, and echocardiographic findings in patients with hypothyroidism to better understand the cardiovascular implications and to inform clinical management strategies.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at PMCH, a tertiary care center with a specialized endocrinology unit, from July 2022 to June 2023.

Participants: A total of 300 participants diagnosed with hypothyroidism were enrolled in the study.

The participants were selected through a non-probability consecutive sampling method.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of hypothyroidism based on laboratory tests (elevated TSH levels and low T3/T4 levels).
- Patients who have been on stable thyroid hormone replacement therapy for at least 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known cardiovascular diseases unrelated to hypothyroidism.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with other endocrine disorders (e.g., diabetes mellitus, adrenal insufficiency).
- Patients with a history of neck surgery or radiation therapy.
- Patients unwilling to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled. Information bias was minimized by using standardized procedures for data collection, and all measurements were performed by trained and experienced healthcare professionals. Confounding factors were controlled through exclusion criteria and statistical adjustments.

Data Collection: Data collection involved a comprehensive review of patient medical records, physical examinations, and diagnostic tests. The following data were collected for each participant:

- Demographic information (age, gender, etc.).
- Clinical history and duration of hypothyroidism.
- Electrocardiographic (ECG) findings.
- Neck ultrasound (USG) findings.
- Echocardiographic parameters.

Procedure: Each participant underwent a standard 12-lead ECG, a detailed neck ultrasound focusing on the thyroid gland, and a comprehensive echocardiographic evaluation. The tests were performed by qualified technicians under the supervision of an experienced endocrinologist. The findings from each diagnostic test were documented systematically.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, including mean, median, and standard deviation, were used to summarize continuous variables. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Comparative analyses between different groups were performed using t-tests or chi-square tests, as appropriate. Correlation analyses were conducted to assess the

relationships between ECG, USG, and echocardiographic findings. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 300 participants were

enrolled in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.6 ± 12.3 years, with a majority being female ($n = 220, 73.3\%$). The average duration of hypothyroidism among participants was 7.2 ± 4.1 years. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD / n (%)
Age (years)	45.6 ± 12.3
Gender	
- Male	80 (26.7%)
- Female	220 (73.3%)
Duration of Hypothyroidism (years)	7.2 ± 4.1
Thyroid Hormone Replacement Therapy	
- Levothyroxine	300 (100%)
- Stable Therapy (≥ 6 months)	300 (100%)

Electrocardiographic (ECG) Findings: ECG findings revealed a variety of abnormalities in the study population. The most common finding was sinus bradycardia, observed in 102 participants (34%). Prolonged QT interval was noted in 78

participants (26%). Low voltage QRS complexes were found in 65 participants (21.7%). Table 2 presents the distribution of ECG findings among the participants.

Table 2: Electrocardiographic Findings in Hypothyroidism Patients

ECG Finding	n (%)
Sinus Bradycardia	102 (34.0%)
Prolonged QT Interval	78 (26.0%)
Low Voltage QRS Complexes	65 (21.7%)
Atrial Fibrillation	20 (6.7%)
Normal ECG	35 (11.7%)

Neck Ultrasound (USG) Findings: Neck ultrasound findings showed diffuse thyroid enlargement in 180 participants (60%), and 45 participants (15%) had a nodular thyroid. Hypoechoic texture was observed in 210 participants (70%), indicating a chronic inflammatory process. Table 3 summarizes the USG findings.

Table 3: Neck Ultrasound Findings in Hypothyroidism Patients

USG Finding	n (%)
Diffuse Thyroid Enlargement	180 (60.0%)
Nodular Thyroid	45 (15.0%)
Hypoechoic Texture	210 (70.0%)
Calcifications	30 (10.0%)
Normal Thyroid Appearance	35 (11.7%)

Echocardiographic Findings: Echocardiographic assessment revealed left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in 90 participants (30%), while 60 participants (20%) had mild pericardial effusion. Left ventricular hypertrophy was observed in 75 participants (25%). Table 4 details the echocardiographic findings.

Table 4: Echocardiographic Findings in Hypothyroidism Patients

Echocardiographic Finding	n (%)
Left Ventricular Hypertrophy	75 (25.0%)
Left Ventricular Diastolic Dysfunction	90 (30.0%)
Mild Pericardial Effusion	60 (20.0%)
Aortic Root Dilatation	25 (8.3%)
Normal Echocardiogram	50 (16.7%)

Correlation Between ECG, USG, and Echocardiographic Findings: Statistical analysis

using Pearson's correlation coefficient showed significant correlations between ECG abnormalities

and echocardiographic findings. Sinus bradycardia was significantly associated with left ventricular diastolic dysfunction ($r = 0.48, p < 0.001$). Prolonged QT interval was moderately correlated with mild pericardial effusion ($r = 0.32, p < 0.05$). There was also a significant correlation between hypoechoic thyroid texture on USG and left ventricular hypertrophy on echocardiography ($r = 0.45, p < 0.01$).

Discussion

In this study, a cohort of 300 patients with a diagnosis of hypothyroidism had their ECG, USG, and echocardiogram data thoroughly evaluated. According to the demographic data, participants were overwhelmingly female, which is in line with the fact that women are more likely than males to have hypothyroidism. The majority of the patient group was chronic, as evidenced by the disease's average duration of almost seven years. Notable electrocardiographic results showed that sinus bradycardia, which affected 34% of the subjects, was the most frequent abnormality. This is consistent with hypothyroidism's known effects on the cardiovascular system, which include a possible drop in heart rate due to low thyroid hormone levels. In line with earlier research, the extended QT interval seen in 26% of participants indicates a higher risk.

Notable electrocardiographic results showed that sinus bradycardia, which affected 34% of the subjects, was the most frequent abnormality. This is consistent with hypothyroidism's known effects on the cardiovascular system, which include a possible drop in heart rate due to low thyroid hormone levels. According to earlier research, 26% of individuals had a prolonged QT interval, which raises the possibility of arrhythmias in this population. In 21.7% of the patients, low voltage QRS complexes were seen, which may be a sign of myxedema or pericardial effusion, both of which are common in severe hypothyroidism. According to the results of the neck ultrasonography, 60% of the subjects showed widespread thyroid enlargement, and 70% had a hypoechoic texture, which is suggestive of chronic thyroiditis or Hashimoto's thyroiditis, which is frequently the cause of hypothyroidism. 15% of individuals had nodules on their thyroids, which indicates that more testing is necessary to rule out any cancer, even though the majority of nodules in hypothyroid patients are benign.

Significant cardiac involvement was seen on echocardiography; 20% of patients had mild pericardial effusion and 30% had left ventricular diastolic insufficiency. These results are in line with the effects of hypothyroidism on the cardiovascular system, where ventricular dysfunction can result from decreased cardiac

output and increased systemic vascular resistance. As the heart makes up for the changed haemodynamic state, the existence of left ventricular hypertrophy in 25% of participants may indicate the severity and chronicity of the condition.

Significant connections between ECG anomalies and echocardiographic findings were discovered in the study, which is noteworthy. The substantial correlation between sinus bradycardia and left ventricular diastolic dysfunction suggests a

A clear correlation between sinus bradycardia and malfunction of the left ventricle during diastole suggests that hypothyroidism directly affects the electrical and mechanical components of heart function. The intricate relationship between thyroid dysfunction and heart health is further shown by the correlation found between pericardial effusion and a prolonged QT interval.

Significant circulatory abnormalities have been repeatedly observed in patients with hypothyroidism, according to recent research conducted in India. In a prospective observational study, 68 patients with hypothyroidism were enrolled. According to the study, low voltage complexes were the most common ECG finding in 25% of the patients, followed by bradycardia in 10.3% and T wave inversion in 23.5% of cases. Moreover, 2.94% of patients had pericardial effusion and 30.8% of patients had grade 1 left ventricular diastolic dysfunction according to echocardiographic evaluations [3].

Similar to this, it was investigated echocardiographic alterations in sixty hypothyroid individuals who had not yet started treatment. The severity of hypothyroidism and several echocardiographic measures, such as increased left ventricular posterior wall (LVPW) thickness, interventricular septal thickness, and the presence of pericardial effusion, were found to be significantly correlated in the study. These results highlight the significance of early diagnosis in reducing the risk of cardiac problems [4].

An observational research on 150 hypothyroid patients at Gujarat's Parul Sevashram Hospital further supports these findings. According to the study, 32.6% of the patients had isolated diastolic dysfunction and 49.3% of the patients had diastolic dysfunction along with pericardial effusion. Moreover, 8.6% of the patients had thicker interventricular septa, underscoring the functional and anatomical heart abnormalities linked to hypothyroidism [5].

And last, 60 hypothyroid patients who were admitted to a tertiary care facility were investigated by Shah et al. in 2021. TSH levels were shown to be strongly correlated with both ECG and echocardiographic findings in the study. Sinus

bradycardia was the most prevalent ECG finding, and diastolic dysfunction with pericardial effusion was the most common echocardiographic abnormality. In order to stop the development of cardiac symptoms in hypothyroid individuals, the study stressed the significance of early detection and therapy [6].

Conclusion

As a result of the substantial frequency of abnormalities found in ECG, USG, and echocardiographic evaluations, this study highlights the significance of routine cardiovascular and thyroid imaging in individuals with hypothyroidism. These results emphasise the necessity of integrated care strategies for the management of hypothyroidism that take into account cardiovascular health as well as thyroid function. In this population, early identification and treatment of these issues may enhance outcomes and lower the likelihood of more serious cardiac events.

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